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DEVELOPING HANDS-ON LEARNING APPROACHES TO MATH AND PHYSICS IN K-12 LEVEL LEARNING

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What are session participants expected to learn? How are session participants activated?

This is a workshop focusing on the development of K-12 hands-on activities situated within the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as well as an authentic problem-solving framework. In our workshop, we will discuss our approach for how to create opportunities for both students and educators by making connections between the topics covered in the classroom, their communities, and the environments they live in. Expected learning outcomes for our workshop participants will include learning about our framework for creating hands-on learning activities situated within local contexts.

Approximate Schedule:

- Introductions to understand where participants are joining from both regionally and professionally.
- Review of the SDGs and identification of challenges that participants' local regions face.
- Discussion of the difference between problem-based and project-based learning pedagogies.
- Participants presented with an example activity about Ocean Acidification and then will be asked to construct activities of their own inspired by their local challenges while working in small groups.

Why is the session relevant?

This work is based on two years of summer engagements that the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) has held with its STEAM Camp in Hong Kong. Seeking to enhance existing summer offerings for middle school-aged students (ages 10-14) and local teachers, a two-week experience was developed to give participants the opportunity to engage with a broad range of advanced STEAM content taught in MIT "Mens et Manus"-style with hands-on, learning by doing activities, while being exposed to fundamental math and physics concepts. Using MIT content and inspiration from

the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, students cover these activities during their first week. These were developed for the program to not only be relevant to the students ages but also to encourage thought about challenges they face within their own communities. The community that would be best served by our workshop will be K-12 educators as well as those scholars interested in the development of K-12 STEAM outreach programs and making the UN SDGs more accessible to younger populations; however, all are welcome.

How is this work significant for Engineering Education?

For the purpose of this workshop, the beneficial impacts of this work on Engineering Education can be observed through two lenses: The effect on K-12 STEM, and the effect on higher education individuals and on the groups who support them.

With regards to the effect on K-12, our approach to engineering education is that it can be used as a pathway for teaching fundamental STEM concepts. While there are already ongoing discussions about the best way to approach K-12 STEM, in many cases, engineering is still the “silent partner”. Through our work, we are trying to highlight the engineering component and show that it can be a pathway to teach fundamental concepts like math and physics while at the same time using the principles of hands-on, design-based learning as a framework to teach a variety of STEM related concepts. Furthermore, we are also showing how the SDGs can also be introduced at the K-12 educational level, starting even at very young ages.

Regarding the implications for higher education, more and more universities are currently trying to build a deeper connection with the local and international K-12 systems, and participation in our workshop would enhance the participants’ “know how” on how to develop and implement K-12 STEM outreach programs. Regarding more direct benefits to the higher education level, our current experience shows that as university faculty, students, and staff get involved with the development of such STEAM modules, they have been given the opportunity to further explore and understand international contexts and to get exposed to global STEAM-related challenges, information that can be used to further drive their personal research on campus. Beyond STEAM-related challenges, those involved are also expected to understand a new and different educational system that can possibly alter or enhance their perceptions regarding education. Moreover, when university students get involved with content development, they are also given the opportunity to enhance their own teaching experience by exploring education within a new cultural context and also further enhance their teaching skills by collaborating with experienced local K-12 teachers while also learning from them.

Last but not least, as many engineering schools are interested in globally enhancing student understanding of and attraction to STEAM professions, and these local or international K-12 experiences can provide a new test-bed in regards to understanding global perceptions and challenges on that matter, that can further guide STEAM

education related research. We imagine that many institutions around the globe will also share these aspirations.

How will results be summarized?

Descriptions of the modified activities will be recorded and summarized for viewing after the conference ends.